

COcyber success stories

Spain case study on cybersecurity technology and information transfer

COcyber success stories

To understand how cybersecurity ecosystems evolve across Europe, COcyber conducted four national case studies focusing on Lithuania, Spain, Hungary, and Slovenia.

The studies, brought together in a **comparative booklet**, examined:

- Governance structures
- Technology transfer
- Information-sharing mechanisms
- Dual-use cybersecurity potential

In this context, **Spain** shows how cybersecurity technology and information transfer are shaped by a mature but complex ecosystem, where national security, strategic coordination, innovation capacity, and industrial development all play an important role.

NATIONAL CYBERSECURITY LANDSCAPE

Spain has built a strong cybersecurity governance framework, supported by the National Cybersecurity Strategy and the National Cybersecurity Plan. This framework is coordinated through national-level bodies and implemented through a broad institutional ecosystem, giving Spain a mature governance structure. At the same time, the case highlights persistent structural challenges, including fragmentation across levels of administration, uneven cyber maturity among SMEs, and a significant cybersecurity skills gap.

TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER FRAMEWORK

Spain treats technology transfer as a strategic priority for strengthening national cyber capabilities and reducing dependence on non-European providers. The case points to a range of policy instruments and funding programmes that support the development and deployment of domestic cybersecurity solutions. However, rigid administrative procedures, bureaucratic burdens, and unclear intellectual property arrangements still slow the effective transfer and market uptake of cybersecurity innovation.

INFORMATION-SHARING PRACTICES

Spain has developed a comprehensive structure for cybersecurity information sharing, including a dual national CERT system, formal collaboration platforms, and technical tools for threat intelligence exchange.

These mechanisms provide a solid institutional basis for cooperation. However, their effectiveness is still limited by low trust among stakeholders, legal and compliance sensitivities, and hesitation among private organisations to share sensitive information.

DUAL-USE POTENTIAL

The Spanish case confirms that cybersecurity technologies have clear dual-use potential, with relevance across both civilian and defence contexts. This duality is increasingly recognised as important for national resilience and strategic autonomy. At the same time, the case highlights that dual-use development is still constrained by policy gaps, slow export-licensing procedures, and restrictive conditions that limit faster transfer between research, industry, and operational use.

RECOMMENDATION HIGHLIGHT

Spain's next step is to build on its strong institutional framework by reducing administrative barriers, improving trust in information sharing, strengthening the uptake of domestic innovation, and creating a more coherent governance approach for dual-use cybersecurity technologies.